

DEVELOPMENT OF SOCIO-POLITICAL AND ECONOMIC RELATIONS OF THE REGION

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Abstract: This article provides comments on the strategy of innovation and economic development of the region, and industrial enterprises of the region annually invest in the development and modernization of their production capacities, the development and modernization of information technologies as the main factors of production development.

Keywords: Innovative economic development, strategy, industrial enterprises, modernization, production, regional development.

In recent years, rapid development in various fields has been observed in our country. The word "new Uzbekistan" has already entered the people. It encourages people to develop and innovate. In this regard, for the financial and economic development of the region, it is necessary to develop a mechanism for supporting the region from a national point of view.

Concepts of regional and local economic policy are closely related to the concept of "regional development". VN Lexin and AN Shvetsov understand this as "such a mode of operation of the regional system aimed at positive dynamics of parameters of the level and quality of life." Reproduction of the social, economic, resource and ecological potentials of the population, stable, balanced territory without mutual destruction". At the same time, the concepts "territory" and "regional system" are considered synonymous by them. Under the territory, the authors define a certain part of the social, natural, economic, infrastructural, cultural and historical and spatial potential of the state under the jurisdiction of sub-federal or local authorities.

We are close to such an approach in determining the nature of regional and territorial development. In this case, "Regulation of regional development should be understood as specially organized systematic actions to ensure stable and balanced functioning of regional systems.

The main goal is to improve the standard of living of the population and increase its quality. Such regulation refers to the mandatory functions of any state. As stated by DA Tatarkin, EN Sidorova and OA Kozlov, "The construction of an effective model of economic development should be based on the global trend

aimed at the formation of stable socially oriented self-developing regional systems that create conditions for social stability and economic well-being of the population."

We agree with O. Vnin Kuznetsova's opinion that "ideas of "adapters" are most acceptable for the new Uzbekistan."

In our opinion, reflecting the ideas of those who adapt to the level of regulation, we can conclude that this approach is appropriate in regulating the development of local authorities located in the region and its territory.

At the same time, SD Valentey says: "National regional policy should be based on determining the specific factors of growth or development of the economy of certain subjects of the region."

In the study of policies at different levels of governance, carried out by TV Gritsyuk, great attention is paid to the management of regional development. The author offers a strategic approach to the modeling of regional development processes, fiscal regulation of relations between the center and regions, and modeling of regional fiscal behavior.

OV Kuznetsova understands it as "actions of the central authority, the purpose of which is to selectively influence the economic development of individual regions" describing the state regulation of the economic development of the regions.

It should be noted that the concept of "territorial development regulation" is somewhat broader than the concept of state regulation of the economic development of regions, although it is semantically close.

Taking into account that the article examines the cooperation of regional and local authorities in the process of regional development regulation, we believe that it is necessary to pay some attention to the theories that are the basis for understanding the institution of self-government. The essence of the institution of local self-government is the self-organization of the population, which in essence allows connecting local self-government to the events of community life. On the one hand, local self-government provides public services closer to the population, on the other hand, it provides for the development of citizens' independence, self-management and stability of society and the state.

changed to the principle of "man - society - state". To put it more simply, Uzbekistan emphasizes the need to increase the value and welfare of every citizen. Most importantly, the main idea of the 7 priorities in the development

The main idea of the President's pre-election program was the principle "For human dignity". How to implement legal and organizational-legal ways to restore human dignity in all spheres of our life at national, regional and international cooperation levels? Development strategy has practical answers to this urgent question, with many specific objectives.

The second is the importance of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan at the regional level. Special attention is paid to the important tasks of valuing close brotherhood among the peoples of Central Asia, strengthening beneficial cooperation with neighboring countries, and achieving regional security and sustainable development. The third is the importance of the development strategy of New Uzbekistan at the international (global) level.

"New Uzbekistan - a new worldview" spiritual and educational promotion events are being organized. A 7-direction working group of the Republican headquarters was formed to organize the work of conveying the essence and importance of the reforms implemented in our country to the general public in the neighborhoods. They were assigned tasks such as organizing and coordinating the activities of propaganda groups, preparing and delivering propaganda materials, systematically carrying out propaganda work in neighborhoods by higher education institutions.

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